

Prof. dr hab. Inga Kawka,
Associate Professor,
Faculty of Law and Administration,
Jagiellonian University in Krakow,
Republic of Poland

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LEGAL AND FINANCIAL MECHANISMS TO ADDRESS SOCIAL CONFLICTS IN THE EU GREEN TRANSITION: THE CASE OF COAL PHASE-OUT IN POLAND

Abstract: *This article examines the effectiveness of EU and national legal and financial mechanisms in addressing social conflicts linked to Poland's coal phase-out within the European Green Deal framework. The focus is on the Just Transition Fund (JTF) and related instruments, which aim to reconcile climate neutrality goals with the socio-economic needs of coal-dependent regions. Despite substantial funding and social contracts with miners, tensions persist due to delayed coal phase-out timelines, gaps in regional plans, insufficient stakeholder engagement, and conflicts with EU state aid rules. The study highlights the need for improvements in participatory governance, better alignment between national and EU policies, and prioritisation of projects that create sustainable jobs beyond the coal sector to ensure a just and effective transition that supports social cohesion while meeting climate targets.*

Keywords: *green transition, social conflict, Just Transition Fund, coal phase-out, Poland, EU energy policy, miners' protests.*

1. Introduction

In light of the European Union's climate policy and the objective of achieving climate neutrality by 2050, it is evident that Poland will undergo a transition from fossil fuels to renewable energy sources. Consequently, Polish regions that are economically dependent on the mining sector and conventional energy production may experience significant economic and social repercussions. The decommissioning of coal mines and coal-fired power plants

* inga.kawka@uj.edu.pl, ORCID ID 0000-0001-6909-5798.

may lead to a substantial increase in unemployment and a decline in living standards across entire regions, due to the high degree of economic dependence on coal industry. This, in turn, gives rise to social tensions and conflicts, most notably in the form of intense protests by miners.

The research problem concerns how effectively these mechanisms, especially the Just Transition Fund and related EU and national instruments, address the tensions between climate policy goals and the socio-economic realities of coal-dependent regions. The study investigates why these tools have not resolved the underlying conflicts despite the existence of social contracts with miners and substantial EU funding. The article seeks to answer the following research question: How can legal and financial instruments be improved to ensure that the transition is both effective in achieving climate goals and just for affected communities?

2. Poland energy transition

2.1. Situation in the Coal Sector in Poland

Coal has historically been a fundamental energy source in Poland. However, after the transition to a market economy in 1989, the coal industry proved to be unprepared for competition. Since then, a continuous restructuring process has been underway, aimed at improving the sector's economic efficiency, reducing production costs, and adjusting to shrinking domestic demand. Despite restructuring programs, the industry's economic efficiency remained insufficient, and coal mining companies failed to sustainably compete in open markets (Kaczmarek, Kolegowicz, Szymła, 2022:12-14; Gawlik, 2018: 231-234).

In addition, the use of energy from renewable sources in Poland has shown a growing trend in recent years. The share of renewable energy in total primary energy supply increased from 19.4% in 2019 to 24.5% in 2023. Energy obtained from renewable sources in 2023 mainly comes from solid biofuels (60.1%), wind energy (15.0%) and liquid biofuels (7.7%) (Główny Urząd Statystyczny, 2024a: 14). Coal consumption is declining. Hard coal consumption in 2023 amounted to 55.4 million tonnes and decreased by 14.0% compared to 2022 (Główny Urząd Statystyczny, 2024b: 10).

2.2. Strategic documents guiding Poland's energy transition

The current strategic documents guiding Poland's energy transition provide for the coal phase-out. The Energy Policy of Poland until 2040¹ and the upda-

¹ Ministry of Climate and Environment (2021). Energy Policy of Poland until 2040. Retrieved

bted 2024 draft of Polish National Energy and Climate Plan for 2021–2030² outline several specific objectives, including inter alia the implementation of nuclear energy (starting with the launch of the first nuclear unit in 2033 and followed by the commissioning of six units using Generation III and III+ technology by 2043) and the development of renewable energy sources (particularly through the deployment of offshore wind energy). According to the projections of Poland's updated National Energy and Climate Plan, the share of coal in electricity generation is expected to decline significantly over the forthcoming years. In 2023, coal accounted for approximately 60% of the country's electricity production. By 2030, this share is projected to fall to around 21–22%. Installed coal-fired capacity will be reduced from 31.5 GW in 2023 to 20 GW by 2030. Domestic coal demand will decline to approximately 22.5–30 million tonnes annually, supplied mainly by domestic mining, with imports serving only as supplementary supply. The plan foresees that by 2040, coal will play only a marginal role in the energy mix, accounting for about 1% of electricity generation and producing just 4 TWh of electricity, with installed capacity dropping to 5.6 GW. The use of coal in households will be fully phased out by 2040, replaced by renewable energy sources, heat pumps, energy storage, and other low-emission technologies. This reduction reflects the anticipated transformation of Poland's energy mix in line with EU climate objectives and domestic decarbonisation strategies. (Ministry of Climate and Environment, 2024).

However, ensuring energy security is a fundamental task for every state. Recent geopolitical developments, particularly the war in Ukraine and sanctions on Russia, have revealed how fragile energy supply chains are. This situation has amplified the importance of domestic coal resources in Poland, creating a new context in which the mining sector's role appears more critical than previously assumed. Some authors argue that instead of liquidating the coal industry, Poland should pursue its modernisation and restructuring. They propose innovative solutions, including clean coal technologies, carbon capture, digitisation, automation, methane emission reduction, and improved occupational safety, as part of a sustainable and competitive mining sector aligned with climate goals (Brodny, Tutak, 2022).

18 June 2025 from <https://www.gov.pl/web/climate/energy-policy-of-poland-until-2040-epp2040>.

² Ministry of Climate and Environment (2024), Draft of Polish National Energy and Climate Plan for 2021–2030. Retrieved 18 June 2025 from <https://www.gov.pl/attachment/79b15ec0-b0c7-4825-b2c4-d3cc7c99bb44>. National Energy and Climate Plans are the framework within which EU Member States must notify their climate and energy objectives, targets, policies, and measures to the European Commission. They were established under Regulation (EU) 2018/1999 of the European Parliament and of the Council on the Governance of the Energy Union and Climate Action.

Despite these possibilities, Polish planning documents and policies reflect a different reality. They largely continue to focus on phasing out coal rather than supporting its innovative development, and they fail to address key challenges identified by experts, such as methane management, skills gaps, or employment optimisation. This shows a clear gap between the vision of possible mining sector transformation and the current direction of strategic planning, which still prioritises rapid coal phase-out under strict EU climate policies.

3. Social Conflicts arising from Poland’s Energy Transition

Conflict is a concept often misunderstood and mistakenly equated with violence, particularly in languages of Latin origin, where the term tends to evoke negative associations and is therefore frequently avoided. However, conflict is much richer in meaning. According to Novara (2014), conflict can be defined as a contradiction without components of irreversible damage, where there is the intention to address the problem without harming other parties and to maintain relations between stakeholders, even if difficult and problematic. This highlights that conflict does not inherently imply violence or destruction, but rather represents a situation of opposing interests or views, managed with respect and with the aim of preserving relationships. Thus, social conflict differs from war as it presupposes the possibility of dialogue, negotiation, and resolution without necessarily seeking the destruction of the opposing side. According to Wievorka (2013), social conflict is a social phenomenon that arises when three fundamental elements are present: a) the principle of totality: there is a common sphere of action or a set of issues that are significant for all actors involved; b) the principle of opposition: each party defines itself in relation to an opponent, perceiving the other as an adversary rather than an enemy to be physically eliminated; and c) the principle of identity: each party defines its own position and identity within the context of the conflict (Wievorka, 2013: 700).

The conflict between miners and the ruling authorities in Poland is a classic example of a social conflict because it meets all three fundamental principles. Regarding the principle of totality, both parties act within a common sphere of action concerning the future of the mining sector, which is critical for national economic policy, energy security, and employment. Decisions regarding the closure of mines and coal power plants or restructuring of the sector have far-reaching consequences not only for miners but for entire regions dependent on mining (such as Silesia). As far as the principle of opposition is concerned, miners and government representatives clearly define themselves in relation to one another. The miners see themselves as

the defenders of their jobs, communities, and rights, while the authorities present themselves as responsible for balancing social needs with economic reforms, environmental protection, and European Union obligations. With regard to the principle of identity, both sides are aware of their distinct social roles. Miners identify as a working-class group with a tradition of solidarity and collective action, while the authorities represent the political or administrative elite responsible for managing national resources and implementing policies.

This social conflict has been manifested in numerous strikes and protests throughout Poland's modern history. For example, in the 2010s and 2020s, strikes and demonstrations occurred in response to government plans to phase out coal in accordance with climate policies and European Union Green Deal targets. Most recently on 9 January 2025, thousands of miners marched in Warsaw, demonstrating against government plans to shut down coal power plants. The protest was organised mainly by trade unionists from the Silesian-Dąbrowa "Solidarity" region, with participation from members of the All-Poland Alliance of Trade Unions (OPZZ) and the Forum of Trade Unions. These protests highlight tensions between economic, ecological, and social priorities, and often result in prolonged negotiations, partial agreements, or new protest waves.³

The ongoing protests by coal miners in Poland reflect a complex and multi-layered social conflict triggered by the country's transition toward a low-carbon economy. This conflict can be analytically divided into three overlapping dimensions. Firstly, it is a conflict of interests. In essence, it entails a direct conflict of interests between two opposing stakeholder groups. On the one hand, coal miners are defending their jobs, income, and regional identity, which are closely tied to the continuity of mining operations. On the other hand, national authorities and EU institutions are committed to implementing climate policy objectives, which involve the progressive closure of coal mines and the reduction of fossil fuel dependency. This creates a zero-sum perception, where gains for environmental objectives are viewed as losses for workers and their communities (Zientara, 2009: 45).

Secondly, beyond material interests, the conflict is also symbolic and ideological. In mining regions, coal is not merely an energy source; it is perceived

³ TVN24 (2025). Energetycy i górnicy protestowali przeciwko likwidacji elektrowni, węglowych, 09.01.2025, <https://tvn24.pl/tvnwarszawa/srodmiescie/warszawa-protest-przeciwko-likwidacji-elektrowni-weglowych-9-stycznia-2025-st8251969>; Bankier.pl (2025). Na kolana przed węglem. Rozpoczął się protest w stolicy, 09.01.2025, <https://www.bankier.pl/wiadomosc/Na-kolana-przed-weglem-Rozpoczal-sie-protest-w-stolicy-8871521.html> (retrieved 18 June 2025).

as a lifeline, a cultural symbol, and a cornerstone of regional identity. This vision fundamentally clashes with the EU’s paradigm of a green, carbon-neutral economy, which places climate goals above traditional industrial models. Decarbonisation policies promoted by the EU are perceived by miners as an attack on this identity: a symbolic erasure rather than progress. The clash of imaginaries reveals how coal is entangled with cultural narratives that resist replacement by the green economy’s vision of the future (Smyth, 2024; Brown, Spiegel, 2019: 159; Lechowicz, Kuchler, 2024).

The third structural feature of conflict is the asymmetry of power. Miners and local communities bear the burden of transformative decisions that they had little role in shaping. Decisions about energy transition timelines, funding allocations, and plant closures are typically made by central authorities or EU institutions, leaving affected populations feeling politically disempowered. Although the state has legal and financial tools to manage the transition, it often lacks social legitimacy in the eyes of those most affected.

Together, these three dimensions show that miners’ protests are not simply the expression of economic grievance but rather reflect deeper questions of justice, representation, and dignity. Addressing these tensions requires more than compensation mechanisms; it necessitates inclusive dialogue, recognition of cultural attachments, and a more participatory approach to shaping the energy future of mining regions (Kozłowska-Woszczycka, Pactwa, 2022; Włodarczyk, Herczakowska, 2025). The response to these challenges is the concept of just transition in EU law, which stems from the principle of sustainable development.

4. Coal phase-out and the concept of just transition in the EU

4.1. The origins of the concept of just transition

The concept of a just transition originated in the 1980s within labor union movements in the United States. Most notably, Tony Mazzocchi, the leader of the Oil, Chemical and Atomic Workers Union, advocated for a “Superfund for Workers” to compensate and retrain individuals displaced by environmental regulations, thus laying the sociopolitical groundwork for linking environmental protection with worker justice (Mah, 2023). Over subsequent decades, this idea evolved into a broader international framework prioritising equitable outcomes alongside environmental goals.

According to the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) Glossary, the just transitions are defined as “a set of principles, processes and practices that aim to ensure that no people, workers, places, sectors, coun-

tries or regions are left behind in the transition from a high-carbon to a low-carbon economy” (IPCC, 2022: 1806). According to this definition, just transition calls for focused and proactive actions by governments and institutions to minimise the negative social, environmental, and economic consequences of large-scale economic shifts, while ensuring the greatest benefit for those most affected. Its core principles include respect for vulnerable groups, equitable access to energy, inclusive dialogue with stakeholders, decent employment, social protection, and labour rights. The approach also encompasses fair climate and land-use policies, low-emission economic restructuring, effective retraining programmes, gender-sensitive measures, poverty reduction, and international cooperation. Importantly, it seeks to address past harms and injustices through inclusive and reparative strategies (ILO 2015; UNFCCC 2016).

4.2. Just Transition within the Framework of Sustainable Development in the EU

In the EU law, the concept of just transition is integrally linked with the broader paradigm of sustainable development, defined in the Brundtland Report (1987) as “development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs”. This tripartite vision of economic, social, and environmental development has increasingly become the cornerstone of the European Union’s legal and policy framework. In EU law, sustainable development is not merely a rhetorical objective but a foundational legal principle. Article 3(3) of the Treaty on European Union (TEU) explicitly states that the Union “shall work for the sustainable development of Europe”, encompassing balanced economic growth, a highly competitive social market economy, full employment and social progress, and a high level of protection and improvement of the quality of the environment. These three pillars correspond directly with the operative dimensions of just transition: economic restructuring, social cohesion, and environmental protection. From a functional perspective, it guides legislative and administrative processes, ensuring that all EU policies – particularly those affecting regions undergoing deep structural changes – are aligned with long-term sustainability goals (Kawka, 2024: 60).

The just transition approach operationalises this principle by embedding social justice, employment security, and inclusive governance into the EU’s green transformation agenda. It ensures that economic decarbonisation, a central goal of the European Green Deal (2019) proceeds in a way that mitigates social risks and promotes equality. Moreover, the notion of a social market economy, introduced by the Lisbon Treaty and anchored in Article

3(3) TEU, affirms the EU's commitment to combining economic liberalism with social protection. The establishment of the Just Transition Mechanism reflects the EU's overarching commitment to achieving carbon neutrality by 2050, while simultaneously ensuring social equity and economic cohesion. As such, the Just Transition Mechanism – especially its flagship instrument, the Just Transition Fund (JTF) – reflects the EU's intention to reconcile EU environmental objectives (Articles 191-193 of the TFEU and Article 37 of the CFR) with economic growth and social solidarity.

4.3. Just Transition Mechanism and the Role of the Just Transition Fund

The Just Transition Mechanism (JTM) consists of three interrelated financial instruments: the Just Transition Fund (JTF), a dedicated just transition scheme under the InvestEU programme, and the Public Sector Loan Facility (PSLF). Together, these pillars aim to mobilise approximately EUR 55 billion over the 2021–2027 budget period. These funds are allocated to regions that meet specific eligibility criteria and have approved Territorial Just Transition Plans (TJTps).

The JTF is the central grant-based instrument of the JTM. Its primary function is to provide targeted financial support to territories most negatively affected by decarbonisation. In order to access this funding, Member States are required to develop TJTps, which outline the regional transition strategy, the socio-economic and environmental impacts anticipated, and the mechanisms for public engagement, monitoring, and evaluation. These plans also specify the types of projects to be financed and should reflect local needs and priorities. Eligible projects must be listed in the TJTP and contribute to objectives such as greenhouse gas reduction, job creation and retention, environmental protection, and social inclusion (Regulation 2021/1056; Just Transition Platform Working Groups, 2023). These criteria aim to assist local and regional authorities in selecting and prioritising projects that align with just transition principles. They also promote the ambition of sustainable development in the energy sector and encourage the effective and equitable use of public resources.

4.4. Types of Projects Eligible for JTF Support

The scope of projects eligible for support from the JTF is defined in Regulation 2021/1056. According to Article 1(1) of the Regulation, the JTF aims to “provide support to the people, economies and environment of territories which face serious socio-economic challenges deriving from the transition process towards the Union's 2030 targets for energy and climate and a cli-

mate-neutral economy of the Union by 2050". Article 2 of the Regulation 2021/1056 further specifies that the Fund's single objective is to enable regions and people to "address the social, employment-related, economic and environmental impacts of the transition towards the Union's 2030 energy and climate targets and a climate-neutral economy by 2050", in line with the EU's commitments under the Paris Agreement.

As a result, the JTF support is targeted toward a variety of project categories. Strategic investments in decarbonisation are a primary focus, including modernisation of district heating networks, reduction of industrial emissions, and deployment of low-carbon technologies. Economic diversification measures are also crucial, such as support for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), entrepreneurship, tourism development, and innovation ecosystems, aimed at generating employment opportunities beyond the fossil fuel sector.

Human capital investments, including reskilling and upskilling programmes for workers affected by the green transition, are explicitly mentioned in Article 8(2) of the Regulation 2021/1056, which allows support for job placement assistance, apprenticeships, and education programs. In parallel, energy-related initiatives, such as renewable energy deployment, building energy efficiency improvements, and local energy systems (e.g. biomass, solar, or heat pumps) are also eligible.

The Regulation 2021/1056 also prioritises projects contributing to the circular economy, including waste reduction, resource efficiency, and recycling technologies. Environmental rehabilitation projects, such as land restoration, reforestation, and pollution mitigation in post-coal areas, are another key area of intervention.

Finally, social cohesion is addressed through investments in healthcare, social infrastructure, and mobility services, provided they align with the region's Territorial Just Transition Plan (TJTP). Preparatory actions, such as feasibility studies, pilot initiatives, and technical assistance, are supported to ensure readiness and project quality.

All supported activities must be clearly defined within the TJTPs and selected based on transparent criteria involving local stakeholders, in line with Articles 8 and 9 of the Regulation 2021/1056.

4.5. Implementation of the Just Transition Fund in Poland

Poland has received 3.85 billion EUR from the JTF for the years 2021–2027. In Poland, five regions were granted funding: Lower Silesian Voivodeship

(with 581.6 million EUR allocated to the Wałbrzych sub-region); Łódź Voivodeship (with 369.5 million EUR designated for selected municipalities from the Piotrków and Sieradz sub-regions); Lesser Poland Voivodeship (with 264.5 million EUR for the Oświęcim sub-region); Silesian Voivodeship (which received the largest share of 2,216.9 million EUR for the Katowice, Bielsko, Tychy, Rybnik, Gliwice, Bytom, and Sosnowiec sub-regions); and Greater Poland Voivodeship (with 414.8 million EUR for the Konin sub-region).⁴

As indicated in the Territorial Just Transition Plans, the Just Transition Fund will support Silesia⁵ and Western Lesser Poland⁶ in their transition away from coal mining and combustion. The funding will help residents shift towards a green economy by creating new job opportunities, improving air quality, and supporting SMEs in renewable energy, clean mobility, and other green sectors. In Eastern Greater Poland⁷, the JTF will assist in phasing out lignite mining and coal-fired power, supporting renewable energy development (including green hydrogen production), the circular economy, and building insulation, alongside reskilling of workers from the coal sector. In the Wałbrzych sub-region of Lower Silesia⁸, the support will focus on diversifying the economy through new SMEs and green startups, renewable energy, and energy efficiency measures. The plan aims to foster the creation of new jobs in carbon-neutral sectors. In Łódzkie,⁹ the fund will assist in the

⁴ European Commission – Representation in Poland (2022). 3,85 mld euro dla pięciu polskich regionów. Retrieved 18 June 2025 from https://poland.representation.ec.europa.eu/news/385-mld-euro-dla-pieciu-polskich-regionow-2022-12-05_pl.

⁵ Resolution of the Silesian Voivodeship Board (2022), Terytorialny plan sprawiedliwej transformacji województwa śląskiego 2030 [Territorial plan for a just transformation of the Silesian Voivodeship 2030], retrieved 18 June 2025 from https://transformacja.slaskie.pl/images/Dokumenty/1683275864_wcag_terytorialny_p.pdf.

⁶ Resolution of the Lesser Poland Voivodeship Board (2021). Terytorialny plan sprawiedliwej transformacji dla Małopolski Zachodniej [Territorial plan of just transformation for Western Małopolska], Retrieved 4 June 2025 from <https://bip.malopolska.pl/api/files/2863756>.

⁷ Resolution of the Greater Poland Voivodeship Board (2022), Terytorialny plan sprawiedliwej transformacji Wielkopolski Wschodniej [Territorial plan for the just transformation of Eastern Greater Poland 2030], retrieved 4 June 2025 from https://arrtransformacja.org.pl/wp-content/uploads/2022/12/Terytorialny_Plan_Sprawiedliwej_Transformacji-WW.pdf.

⁸ Resolution of the the Wałbrzych sub-region of Lower Silesia (2022). Terytorialny plan sprawiedliwej transformacji dla województwa dolnośląskiego 2021-2030 [Territorial plan for the just transformation of the Lower Silesian Voivodeship 2021-2030], Retrieved 4 June 2025 from <https://funduszeuodolnoslaskie.pl/node/3884>.

⁹ Resolution of the Łódź Voivodeship Board (2023). Terytorialny plan sprawiedliwej transformacji województwa łódzkiego 2030. Człowiek. Gospodarka. Przestrzeń [Territorial plan for a just transformation of the Łódź voivodeship. People. Economy. Space], retrieved 4

transition away from lignite mining and coal combustion by promoting local SMEs, research infrastructure, renewable energy, energy efficiency, and decarbonisation of public transport, as well as supporting worker retraining for employment in green sectors.

The quality of transition plans and the degree of preparation vary between regions. The Silesian and Greater Poland Voivodeships have prepared the most comprehensive and detailed plans, addressing the challenges of energy transition systematically and supporting sustainable economic development. The Lower Silesian Voivodeship is also well-prepared for the transition in the Wałbrzych sub-region. In contrast, the plans presented by the Lesser Poland and Łódź Voivodeships require significant improvement. In Lesser Poland, the proposed projects, such as educational projects and care services for young children and dependent persons, do not sufficiently contribute to the energy transition. Similarly, the plan for Łódź focuses on the expansion of public facilities, which, while socially beneficial, are not directly related to energy transition goals (Doroszewska-Chyrowicz, 2024). The plan is also missing clear post-coal transition vision and presents minimal job creation strategy. Many of the plans also share common weaknesses, such as delayed coal phase-out timelines, weak engagement with civil society and NGOs, over-reliance on national strategies instead of ambitious regional action, and vague or insufficient employment transition measures for affected workers (Ślimko, Bartecka and Pogoda, 2021).

Two regions did not secure the JTF funding at all. Zgorzelec County in Lower Silesia and the Lublin Voivodeship were excluded because their Territorial Just Transition Plans did not include the closure of coal mines, as a key condition for receiving support. The Turów complex in Zgorzelec extended lignite mining until 2044, while the Bogdanka mine in Lublin is set to operate until 2049.

As highlighted by Doroszewska-Chyrowicz (Doroszewska-Chyrowicz, 2024: 50-53), it is essential for Poland to make full use of the JTF to support the people and areas most affected by the energy transition. Improving the quality of plans, accelerating implementation, and ensuring that initiatives directly support the goals of a just transition should be a priority for both regional authorities and the national government.

5. Social Agreements in the Polish Mining Sector and the EU State Aid Challenge

National legal measures were also supposed to provide a solution to the conflict. Poland has concluded two key social agreements aimed at managing the coal sector’s transition amid the shift toward climate neutrality: the 2021 Social Contract for hard coal mining¹⁰ and the 2022 framework covering lignite mining and the energy sector.¹¹

The 2021 Social Contract for hard coal mining was signed between the Polish government and mining trade unions (NSZZ “Solidarność” and OPZZ). It sets out a timetable for gradually phasing out hard coal mining by 2049. The agreement guarantees miners employment security through mechanisms such as early retirement schemes, severance payments, and retraining programs. It also foresees production subsidies to keep unprofitable mines operational during the transition.

The 2022 social agreement for lignite mining was linked to the creation of the National Energy Security Agency (NABE), which is designed to take over coal-based assets from state-owned energy companies. It includes social protection measures for workers, such as severance packages and energy-sector leave, and was complemented by the 2023 Act on Social Protection for Employees in the Energy and Lignite Mining Sectors.¹² This Act was approved by the European Commission as compliant with EU state aid rules but only insofar as it pertains to social protection instruments (e.g., severance pay and early retirement), not to operational subsidies for mining activities.

However, both agreements face a fundamental obstacle: their core financial provisions – especially production subsidies to sustain mining operations

¹⁰ Umowa społeczna dotycząca transformacji sektora węgla kamiennego oraz wybranych procesów transformacji województwa śląskiego (2021) [Social agreement regarding the transformation of the hard coal sector and selected transformation processes in the Silesian Voivodeship], retrieved 3 June 2025 from <https://solidarnoskatowice.pl/wp-content/uploads/2021/04/Umowa-Spoleczna.pdf>.

¹¹ Umowa społeczna dotycząca transformacji sektora elektroenergetycznego i branży górnictwa węgla brunatnego w tym wydzielenia wytwórczych i wydobywczych aktywów węglowych ze spółek z udziałem Skarbu Państwa (2022) [Social agreement on the transformation of the power sector and the lignite mining industry], <https://www.gov.pl/attachment/17fd4684-4fb2-44df-885c-992ae4e44fbc> (retrieved 3 June 2025).

¹² Ustawa z dnia 17 sierpnia 2023 r. o osłonach socjalnych dla pracowników sektora elektroenergetycznego i branży górnictwa węgla brunatnego, Dz.U. 2023 poz. 1737 [Act on Social Protection for Employees in the Energy and Lignite Mining Sectors of 17 August 2023, Journal of Laws 2023, item 1737], retrieved 3 June 2025 from <https://isap.sejm.gov.pl/isap.nsf/DocDetails.xsp?id=WDU20230001737>.

until 2049 – have not received approval from the European Commission under EU state aid rules. The European Union’s law, particularly under the Treaty on the Functioning of the EU (TFEU) and associated guidelines, prohibits operating subsidies for uncompetitive coal mines as these distort the internal energy market and undermine the EU’s climate objectives. The European Commission has not approved the Polish plan to subsidise coal production as it conflicts with the EU’s decarbonisation goals and the prohibition of aid for coal operations set out in the Council Decision 2010/787/EU (ClientEarth Poland, Instrat Foundation, CAN Europe and Greenpeace Poland, 2021).

This lack of EU approval renders the production subsidies in the social contracts unenforceable at the European level. This misalignment not only delays the transition process but also fuels ongoing disputes between the government, miners, and EU institutions, as well as creating uncertainty for affected regions (Kukula, 2021).

Social contracts with miners are not being renegotiated because public authorities fear escalation of the conflict. Miners’ unions are among the most organised labor groups in Poland, with historical ties to political movements and strong symbolic influence. Their protests often gain national attention and can inspire mobilisation in other sectors, thus increasing the risk of policy destabilisation. The government fears losing narrative control over the transition and facing escalation of broader dissatisfaction. Meanwhile, effective conflict management requires the active participation of all stakeholders at various levels. The first step is to identify and analyse existing human-nature conflicts through tools like conflict analysis, interviews, site visits, and media research. Equally important is the effort to improve scientific knowledge and communication, using articles, reports, and educational events to inform and engage the public. Inclusive dialogue is crucial: fostering exchanges that respect and integrate different competences through active listening and group discussions ensures that diverse perspectives are acknowledged. Additionally, local-level conflict management should focus on inclusive decision-making processes, involving communities in interactive workshops to develop context-sensitive strategies (De Bortoli, Favilli, Maino, 2019: 41).

6. Conclusion

The existing EU legal and financial frameworks, especially the Just Transition Fund and the broader Just Transition Mechanism, have only partially mitigated social conflict in Poland’s coal phase-out process. While these instru-

ments provide substantial financial resources and are based on principles of fairness, sustainability, and inclusiveness, their impact is limited by gaps in implementation and alignment. The Territorial Just Transition Plans (TJTTPs) submitted by Polish regions often lack detail, fail to adequately address local needs, and do not ensure meaningful participation of affected communities.

Social agreements with miners, such as the 2021 Social Contract, have failed to eliminate tensions and protests because they do not reconcile national commitments with EU climate objectives. The timeline for closing coal mines (by 2049) is misaligned with the EU's 2030 decarbonisation targets, creating ongoing uncertainty. Furthermore, the Social Contract remains a political declaration without legal enforceability or EU approval for key provisions, such as production subsidies, which conflict with EU state aid rules. As a result, miners and local communities continue to feel disempowered and unprotected, perceiving the agreements as inadequate to secure their future.

To make the transition both effective in achieving climate goals and just for affected communities, legal and financial instruments must be improved in several key areas. First, they should ensure stronger, mandatory participation of local stakeholders in planning and implementation, fostering inclusive governance and social legitimacy. Second, project selection should prioritise genuine economic diversification, high-quality reskilling, and sustainable job creation rather than symbolic or insufficiently targeted initiatives. Third, there must be a clearer alignment of national strategies with EU climate goals to reduce policy contradictions that fuel further conflict.

To sum up, while Poland's energy strategy outlines clear technical goals, the social dimension remains unresolved. The transition's success depends not only on compliance with EU benchmarks but also on addressing social justice, regional inequalities, and inclusive governance. Transparent planning, locally anchored Just Transition Plans, and reconciliation of conflicting policy timelines are essential to preventing further unrest.

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Prof. dr. iur. hab. Inga Kawka,

Ванредни професор,
Факултет права и администрације,
Јагелонски Универзитет у Кракову,
Република Пољска

**ПРАВНИ И ФИНАНСИЈСКИ МЕХАНИЗМИ ЗА РЕШАВАЊЕ СОЦИЈАЛНИХ
КОНФЛИКАТА У ЗЕЛеној ТРАНЗИЦИЈИ ЕУ:
СЛУЧАЈ ПОСТЕПЕНОГ УКИДАЊА РУДНИКА УГЉА У ПОЉСКОЈ**

Резиме

У Европској унији, прелазак на зелену економију представља велики изазов, посебно за земље попут Пољске које се у великој мери ослањају на производњу и употребу угља. У оквиру Европског зеленог договора, Пољска мора постепено да укида руднике угља и термоелектране на угљ, што доводи до друштвених сукоба, пре свега, због губитка радних места и економске нестабилности у погођеним регионима. У циљу решавања ових проблема, ЕУ успоставља правне и финансијске механизме подршке радницима и друштвеним заједницама у периоду транзиције, попут Фонда за праведну транзицију. Поред тога, Пољска је усвојила националне политике и механизме усмерене ка ублажавању негативних друштвених последица, попут програма за преквалификацију и иницијатива за регионални развој. Међутим, ефикасност ових механизма је још увек под лупом, јер се локалне заједнице и даље суочавају се тешкоћама у прилагођавању зеленој транзицији.

У раду се анализира како правни и финансијски инструменти ЕУ и национални механизми доприносе решавању друштвених сукоба који проистичу из постепеног укидања рудника угља у Пољској, с посебним освртом на Фонд за праведну транзицију (JTF) и сродне механизме. Прелазак Пољске ка климатској неутралности, у складу са политиком ЕУ, изазвао је снажне друштвене тензије, посебно међу рударима. Упркос додељених 3,85 милијарди евра из ЈТФ-а, спровођење је отежано недовољно детаљним Територијалним плановима праведне транзиције (TJPP), slabим укључивањем локалних заједница и регионалним разликама у квалитету припреме. Поред тога, национални социјални споразуми који обећавају субвенције и заштиту радних места нису добили одобрење ЕУ због сукоба са правилима о државној помоћи, што ствара додатну неизвесност. Иако постојећи механизми пружају значајне ресурсе и оквир заснован на правичности и инклузивности, аутор истиче да они у пракси не дају очекиване резултате. Потребно је јаче учешће локалних

актера, боље усклађивање националних планова са циљевима декарбонизације ЕУ и приоритизација пројеката који нуде стварне могућности запослења ван сектора производње угља. Решавање ових проблема може допринети успеху процеса транзиције и постизању равнотеже између климатских циљева и социјалне правде. Аутор закључује да је превазилажење ових изазова неопходно како би се предупредили даљи немири, осигурала одрживост енергетске транзиције и подстакла друштвена кохезија у Пољској.

Кључне речи: *Европска зелена транзиција, социјални конфликти, укидање рудника угља у Пољској, право Европске уније.*